

THE INFLUENCE OF PARENTING STYLES ON SELF-ESTEEM AND DECISION-MAKING STYLE AMONG ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

The mechanism concerning parenting styles, self-esteem and decision-making style has not been adequately explored in the literature. Hence, this cross-sectional study investigated the relationship between parenting styles and their influence on self-esteem and decision-making style among adolescents. A sample of 300 participants (male 168; female 132) was recruited using systematic and convenience sampling methods. Quantitative data collection method was employed to gather insights into the parenting styles and their influence on adolescents development. The participants were students from 5 public senior secondary schools in SSS 1 – SSS 3 in Abraka, Ethiope East of Delta State. Their age ranges from 12 - 20 years. Standardized self-report measures were used for collecting data while Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient was used for testing the two hypotheses. The data collected were analyzed using percentages, frequency, mean and standard deviation for descriptive statistics; Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship among the study variables and to test the stated hypotheses using IBM-SPSS v25 software. Contrary to expectations, the results revealed that different parenting styles (authoritarian, authoritative, permissive, and neglectful) had no significance influence on adolescents self-esteem and decision making style. However, a notable exception was found, as neglectful parenting style showed a significance correlation with decision making style. This suggests that adolescents experiencing neglectful parenting may be more likely to exhibit impaired decision-making skills. The findings contribute to our understanding of the complex dynamics between parenting styles and adolescents development, highlighting the need for further research into the nuanced relationships between parenting practices and adolescents outcomes.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Parenting styles, which are the methods and techniques parents use to raise their kids, have been shown to be crucial in determining how children view themselves in the eyes of others, how they make decisions, and how they feel about themselves (Okunlola *et al.*, 2020). Scholars have discerned a number of prevailing parenting approaches, broadly categorized into four primary groups: authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful. Different combinations of parenting behaviors, expectations, and responsiveness to their children are included in each style (Adimora *et al.*, 2015). The Baumrind's Parenting Typology is a unique classification of parenting approaches, which describe parents in four categories: responsiveness vs unresponsiveness; demanding vs undemanding (Baumrind, 1967). These four forms the basic elements that shape parenting (Baumrind, 1971). Parenting style is a psychological description of standard strategies that parents use in their child rearing efforts (Adimora *et al.*, 2015). Parenting style describes the approaches parents adopt for the overall upbringing of their children. Different types of parenting styles have been identified: Positive parenting; affectionless control (McCabe & Shaw, 2010); and the Baumrind Parenting Typology (Baurind 1971), among others. Of all these types of parenting styles, Baumrind typology has gained the highest popularity. Since parental roles are essentially formative, their influence in the socialization of children

cannot be over-emphasized. Konnie and Alfred, (2013) revealed that parenting style has influence on students' social development. Konnie and Alfred, (2013) inferred that authoritative parenting based on reasoning, understanding, consensus and trust resulted in pro-social behaviour while authoritarian parenting based on strict rules, force, threat, verbal and physical punishments resulted in anti-social behaviour. Evidence suggests that there is a relationship between authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles and children's social perception and development. Children of authoritative parents behave better than those of authoritarian parents and vice- verse (Uka & Berisha, 2019).

The authoritative parenting style, characterized by warmth, support, clear communication, and reasonable expectations, has been shown to have positive effect on children. Studies suggest that children raised by authoritative parents tend to exhibit higher self-esteem, better social skills, and more adaptive decision-making abilities (Adimora *et al.*, 2015). This parenting style fosters an environment that encourages independence while maintaining healthy boundaries, leading to the development of confident and socially adept individuals (Okunlola *et al.*, 2020).

The authoritarian parenting style, characterized by high demands, strict rules, and low warmth, has shown associations with lower self-esteem, potentially hindered social perception, and a tendency towards more rigid decision-making patterns. Children brought up under authoritarian parenting struggle with self-confidence due to the emphasis on

obedience rather than nurturing autonomy, potentially impacting their social interactions and decision-making processes (Niaraki & Nahimi, 2013).

Permissive parenting, marked by high warmth but few demands and rules, contribute to mixed outcomes in children. While these children exhibit high self-esteem due to the supportive environment, they face challenges in social perception and decision-making, as the lack of structure and guidance could hinder the development of crucial skills such as self-discipline and responsible decision-making (Garcia & Santiago, 2017). According to Bakar, *et al.*, (2012), children from this background interestingly tend to be friendly, sociable, creative and with a high level of wellbeing. They are however often aggressive, verbally impulsive and highly confrontational, resistant when limits or boundaries are set for them and with lower levels of achievement. Using Baumrind's dimensions of parenting styles, it is clear neglectful parenting style is low in four dimensions of disciplinary strategies, warmth and nurturance, communication styles and expectations of maturity and control. Due to the lack of care and discipline for the child, as the name of the style suggests, parents are usually uninvolved in the child's life in general. Maccoby and Martin (1983) were of the view that this style of parenting is low in both dimensions (i.e., the degree of responsiveness and demandingness) and also believed to be the most detrimental of the four types of parenting styles on children's and adolescents' development. The absence or low levels of show of the four dimensions of parenting by

parents thereby making them neglectful tend to have various impacts on the child (Odame-Mensah 2018).

Self-esteem is confidence in our ability to think; confidence in our ability to cope with basic challenges of life; confidence in our right to be successful and happy; feelings of being worthy, deserving, entitled to assert our needs and wants, achieve our values, and enjoy the benefits of our efforts. Self-esteem encompasses all these characteristics (Zakeria & Karimpou 2011). But it is most importantly a personal judgment of self and sense of worth primarily based upon externally imposed criteria. Externally imposed criteria include societal judgments or assumptions, family values, or perceived success and failures in various areas of life. Self-esteem is described as a personal evaluation that an individual makes of her or himself, their sense of their own worth, value, importance, or capabilities (Zakeria & Karimpou 2011). Gesinde (2011) reports that consistent evidence across studies showed that parental emotional maltreatment of children contributed to negative self-concept of adolescents. The role of healthy self-esteem in the lives of adolescents cannot be over emphasized as it is very critical to their functionality.

Decision-making has been described as making selections from the given alternatives, it is a continuous process to negotiate the best course of action for a range of situations (Altaf *et al.*, 2021). This study is interested in decision making styles that children adopt in dealing with their day-to-day matters. Decision making is one of the most complicated processes while considering the nature of cognitive approaches or human

thinking. Decision-making differs from one individual to another (Altaf *et al.*, 2021). Child-rearing is crucial in supporting the improvement related to positive judgmental styles among children (Riaz *et al.*, 2012). Decision-making ability is a vital part of transition in child development in life. If a child has rightly developed decision-making ability, he will make his decisions impartial to others. Parenting performs a crucial role in growing decision-making competencies (Rizvi & Najam 2015). Decision-making style has been defined as an individual's typical model of interpreting and responding to decision-making tasks (Driver, 1979; Harren, 1979). Decision-making engages many cognitive processes such as information gathering and processing, problem solving, judgement, memory and learning. Evidence suggests that many adolescents by the age of 15 demonstrate the ability to make correct choices; further they have the capacity for creative problem solving and they are able to understand the phases involved in systematic decision-making. They also demonstrate a better personal control and responsibility for choices, identifying a larger range of risks and benefits (Mann, Harmoni, & Power, 1989).

1.2 Statement of the problem

The way and manner children are brought up is reckoned to be very essential to the development of the growing child. The way parents take care of their children impacts on the latter's personality development and their ways of interacting with social and close relations. This role is very influential in children's development. Child development, psychologists have particularly paid attention to this phenomenon and that many studies

have been conducted to ascertain the veracity of the issue. Most of these studies mainly investigated the influence of parenting styles on children's academic performance at school. There is, however, dearth of data on the influence of parenting styles on children self-esteem, and decision-making style which is considered a non-academic gain.

The impact of parenting styles on children's psychological development reveal concerning repercussions; authoritarian parenting, characterized by stringent rules and punitive measures, tends to encourage lower self-esteem in children due to constant criticism and strict control, inhibiting their confidence and self-worth. Conversely, permissive parenting, marked by a lack of boundaries and guidance, lead to either inflated self-esteem or struggles with decision-making and personal responsibility, creating uncertainty and affecting a child's sense of self.

In regards to decision-making abilities, authoritarian parenting's restricted autonomy and emphasis on compliance hinder a child's capability to make independent decisions, fostering dependence or instilling fear when faced with choices. On the other hand, permissive parenting's absence of clear guidance leaves children grappling with decision-making, leading to impulsivity or indecisiveness, affecting their ability to navigate various situations and make sound judgments.

This gap in literature provides valuable insights into the influence of parenting styles on self-esteem and decision-making style among adolescents, there is a noticeable gap that requires further exploration. The majority of studies have primarily focused on

Western cultural contexts, particularly in the United States and Europe. Limited attention has been given to understanding these dynamics within diverse cultural settings, such as the specific socio-cultural context of Delta State, Nigeria. Therefore, there is a need for research that explores the interplay between parenting styles and the psychosocial development of children, in a culturally nuanced environment, considering factors unique to the local context. This study aims to address this gap by examining the influence of parenting styles on self-esteem, and decision-making style among adolescents in Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

1. To what extent does parenting styles influence self-esteem?
2. To what extent does parenting styles influence decision-making style?

1.4 Objective of the study

The main objective of the study is to examine the influence of parenting styles on self-esteem, and decision-making style among adolescents.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the influence of parenting styles on self-esteem among adolescents
- ii. Examine the influence of parenting styles on decision making style among adolescents

1.5 Significance of the study

Parenting styles and its association with self-esteem and decision making of adolescents have received good attention in the literature but limited to western and Asian

cultures, leaving a major gap in African research in this area. In Nigeria in particular, parenting style studies are still emerging and the few existing studies have focused on finding links between parenting styles and several other outcomes among adolescents, and not self-esteem and decision making. This dearth in literature motivated the need to systematically examine the parenting styles and children self-esteem and decision-making style. The significance of this study is multifaceted and impactful across various domains. One of which is in child development, understanding how different parenting styles affect these crucial aspect helps in comprehending the nuances of child development. It provides insights into how parental behavior shapes a child's psychological and social growth, aiding in the formulation of strategies to foster healthier developmental trajectories.

Mental health and well-being, researching the influence of parenting styles on self-esteem, and decision-making can shed light on factors that contribute to mental health issues in children. Identifying these connections is pivotal in devising preventive measures and interventions to promote better mental health outcomes.

For educational strategies, recognizing the relationship between parenting styles, self-esteem and decision-making style of adolescents can assist educators in tailoring teaching methodologies that accommodate diverse psychological inclinations and decision-making abilities among students.

Again, for parental guidance and support, this study can serve as a guide for parents, empowering them with knowledge about the potential impacts of their parenting styles on

their children's self-esteem, and decision-making. It facilitates informed and conscious parenting, fostering a supportive environment for the child's holistic growth.

Finally, for intervention and support programs, findings from this study can also inform the development of intervention programs targeted at children experiencing challenges with self-esteem, social and decision-making, tailoring support mechanisms based on identified parenting styles.

1.6 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The scope of the study included the influence of parenting styles on self-esteem, and decision-making style among adolescents in Abraka, Ethiope East Local Government Area of Delta State. Abraka in Ethiope East Local Government Area was chosen as a case study; hence, the study is delimited to public senior secondary school students in Abraka.

1.7 Operational Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined as they are conceptualized in this study.

Authoritarian Parenting Style: Is high in strict discipline, maturity expectations, as well as parent-child communications. It is low in warmth and show of affection, low in child-parent communication and hardly considerate of children's opinion (Niaraki & Nahimi, 2013; Garcia & Santiago, 2017).

Authoritative Parenting Style: The authoritative parenting style tends to present a balanced parenting approach that is high on warmth and communication and moderate on discipline and expectations of maturity (Niaraki & Nahimi, 2013). It allows an open home

environment which fosters great emotional support, independence, social and academic competence, self-reliance for children (Akinsola, 2013; Garcia & Santiago, 2017).

Decision -making: Has been described as making selections from the given alternatives, it is a continuous process to negotiate the best course of action for a range of situations (Altaf *et al.*, 2021).

Decision-making Style: Has been defined as an individual's typical model of interpreting and responding to decision-making tasks (Driver, 1979; Harren, 1979).

Neglectful Parenting Style: Neglecting parents are those that show very low level of involvement as well as strictness with their child (Kremers *et al.*, 2003).

Parenting Styles: Describes the approaches parents adopt for the overall upbringing of their children. Different types of parenting styles have been identified: Positive parenting; affectionless control (McCabe & Shaw, 2010); and the Baumrind Parenting Typology (Baurind 1971).

Parenting Typology: This is a unique classification of parenting approaches, which describe parents in four categories: responsiveness vs unresponsiveness; demanding vs undemanding (Baumrind, 1967).

Permissive Parenting Style: Has few behavioural expectations for the child. It is indulgent, lenient, nontraditional and high in responsiveness, but low in control or exigency (Deshpande & Chiabari, 2013; Garcia & Santiago, 2017).

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Self-esteem: Is described as a personal evaluation that an individual makes of her or himself, their sense of their own worth, value, importance, or capabilities (Zakeria & Karimpou 2011).

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section is to review the relevant literature related to the problem under investigation. The purpose of this chapter is to provide a conceptual, theoretical and empirical groundwork on which the study's design and hypotheses are premised. First, the existing literature on the variables under investigation is undertaken. Second, theoretical literature is reviewed to give context to the hypothesized relationship. Last, the empirical relationships between the variables are reviewed, and the hypotheses are stated. The chapter has the following subheadings:

- Conceptual Overview of Parenting Styles
- Conceptualization of Self-esteem
- Conceptualization of Decision-Making Style
- Theoretical Framework
- Empirical Review and Development of Hypotheses

2.1 Parenting Styles

According to Nwanzu (2016), differences in how parent(s) raised their child is captured in the term parenting styles. The way or pattern in which parents train their children is parenting style. It includes different behaviours in different combinations, Syeda and Fakhra (2018). Parents play a dominant role in molding and shaping the behavior of

children, Sunita *et al.* (2022). Parenting styles are the methods and techniques parents use to raise their kids.

Parenting styles across the years have a significant effect on the child and adolescent development, Narito *et al.* (2019). According to Abdul and Abidha (2014) parenting can be defined as activities of parents with an aim of helping their child to bring forth. The Baumrind's Parenting Typology is a unique classification of parenting approaches, which describe parents in four categories: responsiveness vs unresponsiveness; demanding vs undemanding (Baumrind, 1967). Parenting styles are in four facets; Authoritative, authoritarian, permissive and neglectful. Abdul and Abidha (2014), identified 10 items peculiar with authoritative parenting style such as, firm and consistent control, monitor and impact clear standard for their children's conduct, give priority to child's needs and ability, implying age appropriate maturity demands, encouraging children to be independent, attentive, forgiving, encouraging autonomy and offering demographic climate. Authoritarian parents are highly demanding and controlling, Syeda and Fakhra (2018). In this form of parenting style, the parents are rigid, make strict rules which the children must adhere to. Children brought up under authoritarian parenting struggle with self-confidence due to the emphasis on obedience rather than nurturing autonomy, potentially impacting their social interactions and decision-making processes (Niaraki & Nahimi, 2013). Permissive parenting, marked by high warmth but few demands and rules, contribute to mixed outcomes in children. Narito *et al* (2019), proposed thus,

permissive (low level demandingness and low level of responsiveness). Parents do not exact much demand and responsibility on the children. More so, there is low warmth, low control and low in nurture, there are no strict rules and less punishment. The neglectful parenting style is low in the four dimensions of parenting, according to Maccoby and Martin (1983) this style of parenting is low in both dimensions (i.e., the degree of responsiveness and demandingness) and also believed to be the most detrimental of the four types of parenting styles on children's and adolescents' development. This is a negative parenting strategy.

In today's parenting style research therefore, four parenting styles are duly recognised; authoritative (high on demandingness and responsiveness), authoritarian (high on demandingness but low on responsiveness), permissive (low on demandingness but high on responsiveness), and neglecting (low on both demandingness and responsiveness, Maccoby & Martin, 1983).

2.1.2 Authoritative Parenting Style

Baumrind first introduced the concept of authoritative parenting style. According to Baumrind (1966), the authoritative parents provide guidance to their children on issue oriented and rational manner. Since the level of demandingness is higher in this parenting style, parents usually welcome effective communication as well as effective relationship between them (Piko & Balazs, 2012). Hoskins (2014) points out that authoritative parents display more demandingness and responsiveness by exhibiting more supportive towards

harsh behavior. These parents encourage verbal give-and take, express reasoning behind rules and use power, reason, and shaping to strengthen objectives. This style of parenting is more associated with positive children's outcomes. As a result, it is found as most beneficial and effective style of parenting among most of the families. In other words, authoritative parenting style fosters positive well-being of adolescents. For parents to be classified as authoritative, they should fulfill the criterion proposed by Baumrind; however, for parents to be categorized as authoritative, they should have low score in terms of passive acceptant. Nijhof and Engels (2007) have a firm belief that authoritative parenting style plays an influential role in the development of healthy adolescent psychologically and socially. This is particularly because authoritative parenting style helps the children to develop higher level of self-reliance, self-esteem and ability to employ effective coping strategies, while developing positive self-image (Parker & Benson, 2004). The authoritative parenting style tends to present a balanced parenting approach that is high on warmth and communication and moderate on discipline and expectations of maturity (Niaraki & Nahimi, 2013). It allows an open home environment which fosters great emotional support, independence, social and academic competence, self-reliance for children (Akinsola, 2013; Garcia & Santiago, 2017).

2.1.3 Authoritarian Parenting Style

The authoritarian parents attempt to evaluate, shape and control the attitudes as well as behavior of their children in line with set standards of conduct, known as absolute

standard. In the light of this absolute standard, children are supposed to follow very strict rules defined by their parents. In case the children fail to comply with such rules they are punished. Cherry (2015) points out that authoritarian parents usually fail to come up with reasoning behind such rules. According to Hoskins (2014), authoritarian parents exhibit low responsiveness and they are highly demanding. In this style of parenting, parents emphasize on conformity and obedience and thus expect that they are obeyed without explanation in a less warm environment. Furthermore, authoritarian parents display low level of engagement and trust toward their children. They most often discourage open communication and make strict control of a child's behaviour. In other words, it is widely believed that an authoritarian parent is forceful, punitive and believes that a child should adhere to work in accordance to ethics and should be obedient. In the authoritarian parenting style, parents are more concerned with the traditional family structure; therefore, they limit the child's autonomy along with the parent-child relationship. Since the foremost concern of this parenting style rests within the traditional family structure, the child is demanded to adhere to parent's orders without any questions; therefore, it can be argued that authoritarian parenting style tends to rely on rules that are considered as concrete. According to Nijhof and Engels (2007), the authoritarian parenting style is related with the lower level of ability and self-confidence to employ coping mechanisms among adolescents and thus restricts a child to explore his/her capabilities and social interactions, eventually resulting in the child's dependence on parental guidance and direction.

The authoritarian style is high in strict discipline, maturity expectations, as well as parent-child communications. It is low in warmth and show of affection, low in child-parent communication and hardly considerate of children's opinion (Niaraki & Nahimi, 2013; Garcia & Santiago, 2017). Ultimately, the children from this background are known to be anxious, withdrawn, with lower levels of wellbeing, and so on. (Bakar, Ahmad, Dolah, Halim & Anuar, 2012).

2.1.4 Permissive Parenting Style

According to Baumrind (1966), permissive parents attempt to behave in acceptant, affirmative and non-punitive manner toward their children's impulses, actions and desires. Considering the definition proposed by Baumrind that this parenting style tends to have a higher level of responsiveness, it implies that a responsive parent is more likely to define and determine rules associated with family, while encouraging the adolescents to consider it as a resource (Johnson & Kelley, 2011). Permissive style of parenting has few behavioural expectations for the child. It is indulgent, lenient, nontraditional and high in responsiveness, but low in control or exigency (Deshpande and Chiabari, 2013; Garcia & Santiago, 2017). Permissive parents are high in nurturance and acceptance but highly undemanding of compliance and conformity to standards (Driscoll, 2013; Gracia & Santiago, 2017). They are often too open and kind; and as long as a child's action or decision does not bring physical harm, they accept and support, so as to avoid confrontation (Gracia & Santiago, 2017). Children from this background interestingly tend to be friendly,

sociable, creative and with a high level of wellbeing (Bakar, et al., 2012). They are however often aggressive, verbally impulsive and highly confrontational, resistant when limits or boundaries are set for them and with lower levels of achievement (Bakar, et al., 2012).

2.1.5 Neglectful Parenting Style

Neglecting parents are those that show very low level of involvement as well as strictness with their child (Kremers et al., 2003). According to Hoskins (2014), permissive parents can be characterized as exhibiting low level of demandingness and high level of responsiveness, whereas neglecting parents are neither responsive nor demanding. They behave in a manner that is more affirmative toward the impulses, actions and desires of adolescent while consulting with them about family decisions. In addition, they tend to avoid engaging in behavioral control, do not set rules and set a small number of behavioral expectations for their adolescents. From this perspective, it can be stated that permissive parents actually allow the adolescents to actively participate without being concerned for their actions. The neglectful or uninvolved parenting style is low in both responsiveness and demandingness. The parents hardly supervise or exercise control and discipline over the children. Children from this background often show various forms of externalizing behaviours, such as delinquent acts, substance use, etc (Hoeve et al., 2009). Aihie (2016) was found examined the self-esteem outcomes of various parenting styles and showed significant relationship.

2.2 Self-Esteem

Self-esteem is an individual's subjective emotional evaluation of their self-worth or personal value. Morris Rosenberg (1965) defines self-esteem as "totality of the individual's thoughts and feelings with reference to himself as an object". It involves a wide array of beliefs about oneself, and it can be exhibited at different levels, both positive and negative. Positive self-esteem is characterized when a person is confident in his abilities, having a sense of self-worth and able to cope with challenges in life. Individual with positive self-esteem is usually more joyful and he tends to be successful in life (Lynn & Ting, 2019). Meanwhile, a person who has negative self-esteem will neglect his own value, leave them unhappy and feel defeated or depressed. This may lead them to make unwise decision, fall into destructive relationship, or fail to work to their full potential. This shows that self-esteem is vital in a person's healthy development of life (Lynn & Ting, 2019).

Self-esteem an individual's feeling of worth is significant for progress. At the point when children feel certain and secure, they're bound to prevail in school and accomplish individual objectives. As they age, they figure out how to stand up to issues and oppose peer pressure (Vasudeva, 2022). More significantly, having a positive image helps a child with feeling blissful and equipped for keeping up with interpersonal relationships. Building children's self-esteem is a continuous piece of nurturing (Vasudeva, 2022).

Self-esteem can be developed in a multitude of ways, Branden (1969) states that generally self-esteem is formed and altered through a person's beliefs and awareness of

their thoughts, feelings and behaviors. Self-esteem is important because of its role in healthy human development. Abraham Maslow categorized self-esteem as one of the basic human motivations. In his concept of the hierarchy of needs, esteem comes near the top. First comes physical needs, such as food and sleep, then security or safety needs, next social needs, meaning love and affection from others followed by esteem needs, reflection of personal worth and accomplishment, followed only by self-actualization, where one can finally fulfill their full potential (Maslow, 1987). Based on this hierarchy of needs, a child's level of self-esteem is a good way to determine level of success for parenting style. It is clear that one can look at self-esteem in many lights and under multiple contexts.

2.3 Decision Making Style

According to Bednar and Fisher (2003), decision-making is the process of choosing among the available options and is an ongoing dialogue to choose the optimal course of action in a variety of circumstances (Mann, Harmoni, & Powers, 1989). Decision making is one of the most challenging procedures while evaluating the nature of cognitive techniques or human thinking. Individuals make different decisions in different ways (Galotti et al., 2006). Child-rearing is crucial in supporting the improvement related to positive judgmental styles among young people. The social settings are one of the arenas in which decisions are often made, mostly in areas where children live with their guardians. A significant role is played by the societal context as the nature of decision making depends

upon the adaptation and change of actions from the persistently faced situations (Riaz *et al.*, 2012).

Miller and Byrnes (2001) defined decision-making as the process of choosing between different alternatives while in the midst of pursuing one's goal. Several researchers have focused their attention on the relation between personality and decision-making. These models suggested the existence of different typologies of decision-making style (Brew, Hesketh, & Taylor, 2001; Franken & Muris, 2005). Decision-making style has been defined as an individual's typical model of interpreting and responding to decision-making tasks (Driver, 1979; Harren, 1979).

Through decision-making style, we have a way to understand why a person, while facing apparently identical situations, uses such different decision processes (Nutt, 1990). The developmental stage of adolescence is very relevant for studying decision-making competence (Roberto & Fiorenzo, 2009). Some decisions made during adolescence, for example university choice or the involvement in some addictive behaviours, can have relevant consequences for the whole life of the individual (Tuinstra, Sonderen, Groothoff, van den Heuvel, & Post, 2000).

2.4 Theoretical Framework

Established theoretical frameworks can help to further explain self-esteem and how it develops. Harter (1993). One of the leading researchers on self-esteem today, combines James and Cooley's theories of Self-esteem to form a theoretical framework about self-

esteem, its meaning and development. This includes the discrepancy between perception of self and ideal self (and suggests that self-esteem develops from significant social interactions that create thoughts about the self: leading to high or low self-esteem. Underpinning this framework are established theoretical frameworks, including phenomenological theory, symbolic: interactionist theory, humanistic theory, attachment theory and social learning theory. The following provides some detail of each of these theories.

Bums (1979) explored theories relating to self-esteem suggesting that much of the research is based on phenomenological reasoning, which relates to the person's perception of reality rather than the reality itself. He links the phenomenological ' approach particularly to Roger's humanistic theory (self-theory), as it involves the person's perceptions of self, and that the person develops these self-perceptions from the environment, especially the early social environment. Humanistic theory is explained further by Rubin & McNeil (1985) as the way in which each person views and interprets their experiences and how this reflects the understanding of the self. One of the major contributors to humanistic theory, Rogers (1974) states that the most important aspect of the child's experience is that they are loved and accepted by their parent. This helps to explain the basis of Cooley's (1902) proposal of the development of self-esteem, suggesting that the self is constructed by looking into the social mirror, which reflects the opinions of significant others towards the self.

Attachment theory is based on survival and normal development of the child (Bowlby, 1973). A secure attachment in infancy can boost psychological well-being throughout the life span (Bowlby, 1982). Kaplan (1986) states that attachment theory has biological roots but that learning and cognition also play a part. Considering Bowlby's attachment theory, Cassidy (1988) proposes that "experiencing the parent as available, sensitively responsive, and affectively accepting, leads the child to develop simultaneously, both a secure attachment and the sense that as one who merits such treatment, he or she must be inherently worthy".

More specifically, Crittenden (1997) examined attachment theory and psychological disorders, suggesting that the parent's responses to the child can create disorders if the child has felt in danger or fearful of the parent. The child then distorts the bad experience and attachment is distorted, as the child grows up, they have false or no memory of the bad experiences and often see the parent as perfect, whilst they have a lower opinion of themselves. Social learning theory stems from Bandura's work and explains "human behaviour in terms of a continuous reciprocal interaction between cognitive, behavioural and environmental determinants" (Hersenhahn, 1990). Bern (cited in Pierce & Wardle, 1992) provides this example of how social learning theory works: children learn that parents label their observable behaviours and the perception of those labels becomes a source of self-description. This suggests that there is a link between children's self-evaluation, parent's judgment and children's perception of this judgment. However, Noller

and Callan (1991) suggest that the social learning theory involves the child learning from their parent's behaviour, for instance if parents are confident and have little self-doubt then the children will reflect this. Further support of this aspect of the social learning theory and links with self-esteem development is suggested by Sroufe and Fleeson (cited in Cassidy, 1988) who mention that components of the attachment figure become incorporated into the self through the-process of the child's learning or modelling of the parent. They propose that a child's early learning about self occurs mainly within the context of the relationships with significant people in their life.

George Herbert Mead was one of the early and substantial contributors to symbolic interactionist theory. Matsueda (1992), explored the symbolic interactionist theory and found that reflected appraisals of self are substantially affected by parental appraisals. Furthermore, Matsueda, questions Cooley's concept of appraisals being a mirror reflection as a literal interpretation, and that it is more a selective perception of others appraisals that contributes to the self-appraisal. This section has endeavored to explain how these theories relating to self-esteem incorporate the significance of parenting in the development of self-esteem. Harter's combined use of James and Cooley's theories provide a useful theoretical framework for understanding the meaning and development of self-esteem. As mentioned earlier, underpinning Harter's theoretical framework of self-esteem and its development, is a combination of humanistic, attachment, social learning, symbolic interactionist and phenomenological theories.

Therefore, examining Harter's theoretical framework more closely, Cooley's looking glass concept involves teaming from significant others about the self, which relates to a combination of all the above-mentioned theories. Whilst James' theory relates more to what this early learning creates in the person, which is a perception of the self. This view takes in the early learning theories as mentioned above, but then once the self-esteem is developed in childhood as: suggested by the early learning theories, then a phenomenological theory of self-esteem is more appropriate. Therefore, people develop a perception about themselves based on their early environmental interactions and use this as a frame of reference for their behaviour.

2.5 Empirical Review and Development of Hypotheses

The empirical studies which offer support for the purpose for which the research is designed are reviewed in this section. The empirical review is focused on the variables and the possible relationship between the independent variable and dependent variables.

2.5.1 Parenting Styles and Self-esteem

Lynn and Ting, (2019) examine the influence of parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents on their groups from a school Lynn & Ting, (2019) discovered that authoritative parenting style is the most dominant method used in modern family. Through this sort of parenting style, reasoning and communication between parents and children are emphasized, and a balance between warmth and control are discovered. According to Lynn and Ting, (2019) majority of the respondents have mentioned a fair level of self-esteem,

with only one student explains via permissive parenting style and the self-esteem is inferior compared to the others. Subsequently, the differences of parenting styles are influencing the students' self-esteem (Lynn & Ting, 2019).

Hosogi *et al.*, (2012) showed that there was a correlation between certain parenting styles and higher or lower levels of global self-esteem in children. Martínez and García in (2007) found that children of indulgent parents had the highest levels of self-esteem while children of authoritarian parents had the lowest. Another study done later by Martínez & García (2008) found that adolescents with indulgent parents had equal or higher levels of self-esteem than adolescents with authoritative parents. The research additionally showed that adolescents with authoritarian and neglectful parents had the lowest levels of self-esteem. Alternatively, Garcia and Gracia (2009) found that both the children of indulgent parenting style as well as the authoritative parenting styles had the highest levels of self-esteem. It was also concluded in 2007 that the authoritative and indulgent parents' children scored highest on levels of self-esteem (Martínez *et al.*, 2007). Based on these results it is somewhat unclear which of the parenting styles can be labeled most successful on the basis of the child's self-esteem, therefore more research is needed. The quality of supportiveness as perceived by the child predicted higher levels of implicit self-esteem in a study conducted by Antonopoulou *et al.*, (2012). This means it is likely that children with neglecting parents would have lower levels of self-esteem. Furthermore, parents who were recognized as more nurturing (authoritative and permissive) had a positive effect on their

children's self-esteem, while parents perceived to be overprotective (authoritarian) had a negative effect (Wagner *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, emotional warmth (authoritative and permissive) has been positively correlated with higher levels of self-esteem, while negative loving, anger and rejecting were negatively correlated (Erol & Orth, 2011).

Okunlola *et al.*, (2020) find out the prevalent style of parenting among the reviewed studies and establish the relationship between parenting styles and adolescents' self-esteem. According to Okunlola *et al.*, (2020), authoritative parenting style was found to have had the greatest impact on adolescent self-esteem; it enhanced the highest self-esteem levels of adolescents above other parenting styles. Parents who are understanding and supportive tend to help their adolescents retain healthy self-esteem (Niaraki & Rahimi, 2013).

2.5.2 Parenting Styles and Decision-Making Style

Martensen and Gronholdt, (2008) examined parents' perceptions of their children's participation (5-13 years) in the process of making family decisions when buying 14 different product categories. Martensen and Gronholdt, (2008) findings, indicated that parenting style impact children and have a strong influence on the family's decision-making process, especially for products that are relevant to them (such as cereals, juices, soft drinks, and cellphones).

Simanjuntak and Rizkillah, (2020) reported that parents have an essential role to improve the ability of children in decision-making and it is important for parents to begin

to involve children in making decisions and build balanced family communication patterns with the children and parents' orientation. Altaf *et al.*, (2020) examined the relationship of parenting styles with decision-making. Altaf *et al.*, (2020) results showed that Self-concept has significant negative correlation with authoritarian father, authoritarian mother, permissive father, permissive mother, whereas significant positive correlation with authoritative father and authoritative mother on decision making style is also significantly correlated with parenting styles. Parenting style is a significant contributing factor in the lives of adolescents having a substantial influence on their major life domains such as decision making (Rizvi & Najam 2015). Decision-making ability is a vital part of transition during adolescents' developmental phase of life. If a child has rightly developed decision-making ability, he will make his decisions impartial to others.

Prior research establishes that children's involvement in decisions (either deciding with parents or deciding on their own) increases over ages nine to 13 (Yee & Flanagan 1985), while decision autonomy (deciding without parental input) increases over ages 12 to 17 (Dornbusch, Carlsmith *et al.* 1985).

Parenting styles significantly influence children's decision-making style as they grow and navigate the complexities of life. Authoritative parenting, tends to foster children who develop well-balanced decision-making skills. In contrast, authoritarian parenting may lead to children adopting a more rigid and dependent decision-making approach, often relying on external guidance rather than internal reasoning. The permissive parenting style,

result in children who struggle with decision-making independence and lean towards impulsivity. On the other hand, uninvolved parenting, characterized by low warmth and minimal involvement, leave children without the necessary guidance and support, impacting the development of effective decision-making skills (Altaf *et al.*, 2021). Children raised in an authoritative environment are more likely to develop a sense of autonomy and responsibility in their decision-making. This parenting style fosters open communication and encourages children to weigh options, consider consequences, and make informed choices. In contrast, children brought up under an authoritarian parenting style may experience challenges in asserting their preferences and making decisions without relying heavily on external authority figures (Riaz *et al.*, 2012). Permissive parenting, inadvertently contribute to children struggling with self-regulation and facing difficulties in making independent decisions. Uninvolved parenting, lacking emotional support and guidance, leave children feeling unsupported and unprepared for effective decision-making in various life situations.

2.5.3 Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been formulated to guide this study:

H_{0i}: Parenting styles will significantly influence self-esteem of adolescents

H_{0ii}: Parenting styles will significantly influence decision making style of adolescents

CHAPTER THREE

METHODS

This chapter focuses on the research methods of the study with an attempt to provide justification for the choice. This chapter is structured under the following headings:

- Research Design
- Population of the Study
- Sample and Sampling Techniques
- Research Instruments
- Reliability and Validity of the Instruments
- Procedures and Method of Data Collection
- Method of Data Analyses
- Ethical considerations

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts cross-sectional research with a quantitative approach to data collection. This design is suited when the researcher aims to collect data from respondents varying demographics at a point in time using structured and standardized questionnaires in a bid to describe a phenomenon as they occur as is the case in this study. This is therefore the best fit for the objectives of the study.

3.2 Population of the study

The study was conducted in different public schools in Abraka (DELSU Secondary School, Ojeta Secondary School, Abraka Grammer School, Urhuoka Secondary School and Oria Secondary School). The sample comprised of students in the senior classes (SSS 1 to SSS 3).

The population of the study consisted of all the students of the public senior secondary school who range from lower to middle class backgrounds. This is because the participants for the study were chosen from all the classes of the senior secondary school (SSS 1 to SSS 3). The reason behind the adoption of senior secondary students as the main sample of the study was to investigate how parenting styles influence self-esteem and decision-making style among adolescents, particularly in senior secondary students.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

Sampling is the process of selecting a statistically representative sample of individuals from the population of interest. Sampling is a vital tool for research studies because the population under investigation usually consists of many individuals for a research project to include as participants. The main purpose of sampling is to discover principles, which have universal applications. A sample is a smaller representation of larger whole. A convenience sampling technique was adopted. This method selects individuals who present their availability to partake in the study. Specifically, this study used the systematic and convenience sampling method to obtain the appropriate sample from the

large pool of students in the five public senior secondary schools in Abraka. First, systematic sampling was used to select the five schools. This led to the selection of DELSU Secondary School, Ojeta Secondary School, Abraka Grammer School, Urhuoka Secondary School and Oria Secondary School. After the selection of the schools, convenience sampling was used to select students based on convenience and availability. It is a convenience sampling because students who were available, easy to reach, and who met the inclusion criteria were used for the study. Permission was taken from the principals of the schools before commencing the distribution of questionnaires. Three hundred and fifty questionnaires were distributed across the five schools that were systematically selected.

3.4 Research Instruments

Three Instruments were adopted in this study. Specifically, each variable was measured with a prevalidated and reliable instrument found in literature. The instrument includes parental authority questionnaire scale, Rosenberg self-esteem scale and general decision-making questionnaire scale. The instruments adopted for the study were all in their original form and they are further discussed.

Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ)

Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ) was created by John R. Buri in 1989 and the purpose of it was to measure parental authority or disciplinary practices from the perspectives of children at any age. PAQ consisted of 20 items that have 4 subscales based on the parental authority prototypes and each subscale consist of 5 items (Ang & Goh,

2006). There is permissive (P: items 1,2, 3, 4 &5), Authoritarian (A: items 6, 7, 8 9 & 10), Authoritative (T: items 11, 12, 13, 14, & 15) and Neglectful (N: 16, 17, 18, 19 & 20). Participants were asked to respond to each item on a 5-point Likert scales ranging from strongly disagree (scored 1) to strongly agree (scored 5) that will best describe how that statement applies to participants and their parents (Dwairy & Menshar, 2005). Examples are “As I was growing up my mother often told me exactly what she wanted me to do and how she expected me to do it”, “As I was growing up my mother allowed me to form my own point of view on family matters and she generally allowed me to decide for myself what I was going to do”.

Rosenberg self-esteem scale (RSES)

Rosenberg self-esteem scale (RSES) was created by Morris Rosenberg in 1965 and has been widely used in various countries worldwide today. It measures global feelings of self-worth and for use with adult populations. It consists of 10 items that examines rate on a five-point scale from strongly agree (scored 4) to strongly disagree (scored 0) (Kaplan and Saccuzzo, 2008). The RSES had a possible total score ranging from 0-4. The higher scores corresponded to higher levels of self-esteem. The RSE was calculated by adding scores on each item.

General Decision-Making Questionnaire (GDMQ)

The General Decision-Making Questionnaire (GDMQ) is a self-report questionnaire that assesses five decision-making styles: rational, avoidant, dependent,

intuitive, and spontaneous. It was developed by Scott and Bruce in 1995 and has since been widely used in research and practice. The General Decision-Making Questionnaire is based on the idea that people have different preferences for how they make decisions. Some people prefer to make decisions in a logical and systematic way, while others prefer to make decisions based on their gut feelings. The GDMQ helps people to identify their dominant decision-making style and to learn more about how they can make more effective decisions. The GDMS consists of 25 items, with five items for each of the five decision-making styles. Participants rate each item on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being strongly disagree and 5 being strongly agree. The higher a participant's score on a particular style, the more likely they are to use that style when making decisions.

3.4.1 Reliability and Validity of the Instruments

Buri (as cited in Wang and Taylor, 2000) reported that PAQ has good internal consistency measured by the Alpha Cronbach's coefficient that .75 for permissive, .85 for Authoritarian and .82 for Authoritative scale while good stability in test retest reliability that, .81, .86, .76 for Permissive, Authoritarian and Authoritative respectively. According to Buri, Louiselle, Misukanis and Mueller (1988), PAQ has a high criterion and content validity (as cited in Timpano, Keough, Mahaffey, Schmidt, and Abramowitz, 2010). The PAQ was calculated by adding the individual items within each subscale. Higher scores signified a greater level of the specific parenting style (Ang and Goh, 2006).

Research studies have historically reported high levels of reliability for the RSES, internal and test-retest, since its development in 1965. Reliability has been consistently high for diverse groups including adolescents, students, or adults with physical illnesses, mental illnesses, drug addictions, low literacy, and for high achievers or with various translations of the test into other languages. Reliability has also continued to be consistently high throughout administration of the RSES to a wide range of age groups. The RSES presented high ratings in reliability areas; internal consistency was 0.77, minimum Coefficient of Reproducibility was at least 0.90 (M. Rosenberg, 1965, and personal communication, April 22, 1987). A varied selection of independent studies each using such samples as –parents, men over 60, high school students, and civil servants – showed alpha coefficients ranging from 0.72 to 0.87 (all fairly high). Test-retest reliability for the 2-week interval was calculated at 0.85, the 7-month interval was calculated at 0.63 (Silber & Tippett, 1965, Shorkey & Whiteman, 1978).

General Decision-Making Scale (GDMS). The General Decision-Making Scale (Scott & Bruce, 1995) is a 25-item measure that assesses five decision-making styles: Rational, Intuitive, Dependent, Avoidant, and Spontaneous. Participants ranked their resonance to a series of statements on a 5-point Likert type scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Examples of statements within each dimension are as follows, “I make decisions in a logical and systematic way” (Rational), “I generally make decisions that feel right to me” (Intuitive), “I use the advice of other people in making my important

decisions” (Dependent), “I postpone decision making whenever possible” (Avoidant), and finally “I make quick decisions” (Spontaneous). The five styles measured by this scale were confirmed by factor analyses, and the pattern of correlations among the various styles suggest conceptual independence among the five styles. In the current study, the alpha was .70 for Rational, .64 for Intuitive, .77 for Dependent, .89 for Avoidant, and .58 for Spontaneous. The General Decision-Making Questionnaire (GDMS) is a reliable and valid measure of decision-making styles. It has been used in a variety of research studies to investigate the relationship between decision-making styles and other variables, such as personality, cognitive abilities, and job performance. The GDMS has also been used in clinical practice to help people to improve their decision-making skills. The reliability of the GDMS has been assessed using a variety of methods, including internal consistency, test-retest reliability, and inter-rater reliability. Internal consistency refers to the extent to which the items on the GDMS measure the same thing. Test-retest reliability refers to the consistency of scores on the GDMS when it is administered twice to the same group of people at different points in time. Inter-rater reliability refers to the agreement between different raters in scoring the GDMS.

3.5 Procedures and Method of Data Collection

Firstly, permission was sought from the head of the department of psychology to carry out this research. Permission was also sought from the heads of the schools by explaining to them the aims and purpose of the study. After permission was granted to carry

out the research the researcher proceeded to the various classes required for the study. The classes involved were one class each of SSS 1, 2 and 3. In each of these classes he begun by seeking informed consent of the students and once consent was given, he proceeded to issue out the questionnaires to the students in a random manner. Questionnaires were completed without discussion. Students were fully debriefed at the end of the testing session. In each of the classes the questionnaires were issued to both males and females. In all the classes the students were debriefed as to the purpose and aims of the study after the questionnaires were personally collected and any questions the participants had, had been answered.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

Reliability analyses were conducted to determine the consistency of measures in the study. According to the literature, a Cronbach's alpha value greater than .70 is considered acceptable (Howitt & Cramer, 2017), with a higher Cronbach's alpha indicating greater internal reliability. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were reported on all variables. Bivariate correlation was computed using Pearson's r to test the hypotheses; 1 (Parenting styles will significantly influence self-esteem of adolescents), and 2 (Parenting styles will significantly influence decision making style of adolescents).

3.7 Ethical Considerations

Ethics are norms and standards of behavior guiding moral choices about our behavior and relationships with others. Ethical clearance was sought and granted by the

Department of Psychology and the research supervisor. Hence, in this study, issues relating to the ethical conduct of research such as informed consent, confidentiality, privacy and anonymity were upheld. Participants were given full information on the purpose and objectives of the study in order for them to make informed decisions as to whether to partake or not. Moreover, all information concerning the identity and personality of respondents will be treated with strict confidentiality.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

In this chapter, all the results from the descriptive and inferential statistics outlined in the method section following the research's hypotheses outlined in the review section are presented and examined in detail. The influence of parenting styles on self-esteem and decision-making style among adolescents are presented and explained. The instrument of data collection had two parts: section A aiming to describe the Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents; and section B measuring the respondents' response to parenting styles on self-esteem and decision-making style. The responses from the research questionnaire were coded and analyzed using IBM-SPSS v.25.

A total number of 350 questionnaires were distributed to respondents for the study and 300 was successfully retrieved and useful for the study. The 300 questionnaires retrieved represented a return rate of 85.71% of the questionnaires that were distributed.

4.1 Description of the Sample

The personal data of the respondents shows demographic characteristic of the respondents in terms of gender, age, number of siblings, father's highest level of education, father's occupation, class, religion, parents' residence, mother's occupation and mother's highest level of education. The importance of these cannot be over emphasized as they shed light on the background of the respondents which may influence the current topical issues.

Table 4.1.1: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent (%)
Male	168	56.0
Female	132	44.0
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.1 shows the gender of respondents. It indicates that out of the 300 respondents 168 (56.0%) are male, 132 (44.0%) are female. The respondents mean gender = 1.44, (SD = .497). The male respondents are more than the female.

Table 4.1.2: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent (%)
12 – 14yrs	140	46.7
15 – 17yrs	100	33.3
18 – 20yrs	60	20.0
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.2 shows the age range of respondents. It ascertained that out of the 300 respondents 140 are within the age range of 12 - 14 years (46.7%), 100 are within the age range of 14 - 17 years (33.3%), 60 are within the age range of 18 - 20 years (20.0%). Respondents mean age = 1.73, (SD = .773). Those within the age range of 12 - 14 years dominated in the research.

Table 4.1.3: Number of Siblings of Respondents

Number of Siblings	Frequency	Percent (%)
1-4	176	58.7
5-8	124	41.3
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.3 indicates the number of siblings of respondents. It shows that 176 respondents have 1 - 4 siblings (58.7%), 124 have 5 - 8 siblings (41.3%). The respondents' number of siblings have a mean of 1.41, (SD = .493). Respondents who have 1 - 4 siblings made up a large population of the sample.

Table 4.1.4: Fathers' Highest Level of Education of Respondents

Fathers' Highest Level of Education	Frequency	Percent (%)
O/level	146	48.7
Diploma/OND	42	17.3
B.Sc/HND	90	30.0
M.Sc	12	4.0
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.4 shows the respondents' fathers' highest level of education. Out of the 300 participants 146 (48.7%) of the respondents' fathers have O/level, 42 (17.3%) have diploma/OND, 90 (30.0%) have B.Sc/HND, 12 (4.0%) have M.Sc. With the mean of 1.89, (SD = .969). Those whose fathers have O/level are more than those whose fathers have diploma/OND, B.Sc/HND and M.Sc.

Table 4.1.5: Fathers' Occupation of Respondents

Fathers' Occupation	Frequency	Percent (%)
Business	100	33.3
Farming	60	20.0
Handiwork	100	33.3
Civil Servant	40	13.4
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.5 shows the fathers' occupation of respondents. Out of 300 participants 100 (33.3%) of the respondents' fathers are business men, 60 (20.0%) are farmers, 100 (33.3%) have handiwork, 40 (13.4%) are civil servants. Mean = 2.27 (SD = 1.064). Those whose fathers are business men and farmers dominated the sample population.

Table 4.1.6: Class of Respondents

Class	Frequency	Percent (%)
S S S 1	25	8.3
S S S 2	175	57.7
S S S 3	100	34.0
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.6 shows the class of respondents. This indicates that out of the 300 respondents 25 (8.3%) are in SSS 1, 175 (57.7%) are in SSS 2, 100 (34.0%) are in SSS 3. The

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respondents have class mean of 2.26, (SD = .599). Respondents in SSS 2 are the majority in the sample population.

Table 4.1.7: Religion of Respondents

Religion	Frequency	Percent (%)
Christianity	224	74.7
Islamic	47	15.7
Traditional	29	9.7
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.7 shows the religion of the respondents. The table ascertains that 224 (74.7%) of the respondents are Christians, 47 (15.7) are Islams, 29 (9.7%) are traditionalists. Mean = 1.35, (SD = .650). Respondents who are Christians are more in the sample population.

Table 4.1.8: Parents' Residence of Respondents

Parents' Residence	Frequency	Percent (%)
Urban	161	53.7
Rural	139	46.3
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.8 shows the respondents parents' residence. The table indicates that out of 300 respondents 161 (53.7%) of the respondents' parents reside in urban areas, 139 (46.3%) resides in rural areas. Mean = 1.46, (SD = .499). Majority of the respondents' parents reside in the urban areas.

Table 4.1.9: Mothers' Occupation of Respondents

Mothers' occupation	Frequency	Percent (%)
Business	102	34.0
Farming	89	29.7
Handiwork	62	20.7
Engineering	2	0.7
Doctor	3	1.0
Civil Servant	42	14.0
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.9 shows the respondents' mothers' occupation. Out of the 300 participants 102 (34.0%) of the respondents' mothers are business women, 89 (29.7%) are farmers, 62 (20.7%) have handiwork, 2 (0.7%) are engineers, 3 (1.0%) are doctors, 42 (14.0%) are civil

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servants. Mean = 2.47, (SD = 1.641). This indicates that more of the respondents' mothers are business women.

Table 4.1.10: Mothers' Highest Level of Education of Respondents

Mother's Highest Level of Education	Frequency	Percent (%)
Primary	89	29.7
O/level	97	32.3
Diploma/OND	54	18.0
B.Sc/HND	49	16.3
M. Sc	11	3.7
Total	300	100

Table 4.1.10 shows the respondents mothers highest level of education. Out of the 300 respondents 89 (29.7%) of the respondents' mothers have just primary school certificate, 97 (32.3%) have O/level, 54 (18.0%) have diploma/OND, 49 (16.3%) have B.Sc/HND, 11 (3.7%) have M.Sc. Mean = 2.32, (SD = 1.167). Respondents whose mothers have just primary certificates dominated the sample population.

4.2 Testing of Research Hypotheses

The decision rule to be used in testing of the hypothesis is, if critical value (p) $>$ 0.05 for a two tailed test, accept the null hypothesis, if not reject the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1

Parenting styles will significantly influence self-esteem of adolescents.

Table 4.2.1 Pearson's product moment correlation analysis summary of authoritative parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents

Variable	N	M	SD	df	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>p</i>
Authoritative parenting style	300	4.02	.469	298	.01	.00	.859
Self esteem	300	4.08	.362				

Table 4.2.1 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between authoritative parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents. There was a weak positive correlation between authoritative parenting style and self-esteem ($r = .01$, $r^2 = .00$, $N = 300$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, authoritative parenting style does not have a significance relationship with self-esteem of adolescents.

4.2.2 Pearson's product moment correlation analysis summary of authoritarian parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents

Variable	N	M	SD	Df	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i>²	<i>p</i>
Authoritarian Parenting Style	300	3.99	.460	298	.09	.01	.142
Self esteem	300	4.08	.362				

Table 4.2.2 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between authoritarian parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents. There was a weak positive correlation between authoritarian parenting style and Self-esteem ($r = .09$, $r^2 = .01$, $N = 300$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, authoritarian parenting style does not have a significance relationship with self-esteem of adolescents.

4.2.3 Pearson's product moment correlation analysis summary of permissive parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents

Variable	N	M	SD	df	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i>²	<i>p</i>
Permissive parenting style	300	4.021	.606	298	.01	.00	.859
Self esteem	300	4.08	.362				

Table 4.2.3 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between permissive parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents. There was a weak positive correlation between permissive parenting style and

self-esteem ($r = .01$, $r^2 = .00$, $N = 300$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, permissive parenting style does not have a significance relationship with self-esteem of adolescents.

4.2.4 Pearson's product moment correlation analysis summary of neglectful parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents

Variable	N	M	SD	Df	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>p</i>
Neglectful parenting style	300	3.93	.569	298	.09	.01	.135
Self esteem	300	4.08	.362				

Table 4.2.4 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between neglecting parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents. There was a weak positive correlation between neglectful parenting style and Self-esteem ($r = .09$, $r^2 = .01$, $N = 300$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, neglectful parenting style does not have a significance relationship with self-esteem of adolescents.

Hypothesis 2

Parenting styles will significantly influence decision making style of adolescents.

Table 4.2.5 Pearson's product moment correlation analysis summary of authoritative parenting style and decision-making style of adolescents

Variable	N	M	SD	Df	r	r²	p
Authoritative parenting style	300	4.02	.469	298	.07	.00	.225
Decision making style	300	4.09	.270				

Table 4.2.5 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between authoritative parenting style and decision making of adolescents. There was a weak positive correlation between authoritative parenting style and Self-esteem ($r = .07$, $r^2 = .00$, $N = 300$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, authoritative parenting style does not have a significance relationship with decision making style of adolescents.

Table 4.2.6 Pearson's product moment correlation analysis summary of authoritarian parenting style and decision-making style of adolescents

Variable	N	M	SD	Df	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i>²	<i>p</i>
Authoritarian parenting style	300	3.99	.460	298	.02	.00	.748
Decision making style	300	4.09	.270				

Table 4.2.6 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between authoritarian parenting style and decision making of adolescents. There was a weak positive correlation between authoritarian parenting style and decision-making style ($r = .02$, $r^2 = .00$, $N = 300$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, authoritarian parenting style does not have a significance relationship with decision making style of adolescents.

Table 4.2.7 Pearson's product moment correlation analysis summary of permissive parenting style and decision-making style of adolescents

Variable	N	M	SD	Df	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i>²	<i>p</i>
Permissive parenting style	300	4.02	.469	298	.07	.00	.225
Decision making style	300	4.09	.270				

Table 4.2.7 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between permissive parenting style and decision making of

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adolescents. There was a weak positive correlation between permissive parenting style and decision-making style ($r = .07$, $r^2 = .00$, $N = 300$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, permissive parenting style does not have a significance relationship with decision making style of adolescents.

Table 4.2.8 Pearson's product moment correlation analysis summary of neglectful parenting style and decision-making style of adolescents

Variable	N	M	SD	df	<i>r</i>	<i>r</i> ²	<i>p</i>
Neglectful parenting style	300	3.93	.569	298	.47	.22	.00
Decision making style	300	4.09	.270				

Table 4.2.8 shows that a Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was computed to examine the relationship between neglecting parenting style and decision making of adolescents. There was a moderate positive correlation between neglectful parenting style and decision-making style ($r = .47$, $r^2 = .22$, $N = 300$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, neglectful parenting style has a significance relationship with decision making style of adolescents.

4.3 List of Research Findings

The following are the list of the findings in this study:

1. Authoritative parenting style does not have a significance influence on self-esteem of adolescents
2. Authoritarian parenting style does not have a significance influence on self-esteem of adolescents.
3. Permissive parenting style does not have a significance influence on self-esteem of adolescents.
4. Neglectful parenting style does not have a significance influence on self-esteem of adolescents.
5. Authoritative parenting style does not have a significance influence on decision making style of adolescents.
6. Authoritarian parenting style does not have a significance influence on decision making style of adolescents.
7. Permissive parenting style does not have a significance influence on decision making style of adolescents.
8. Neglectful parenting style has a significance influence on decision making style of adolescents.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Discussion

The study predicted that parenting styles will significantly influence self-esteem and decision-making style of adolescents in Abraka, Ethiope East, Delta State, Nigeria. Results from the Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient performed on all data collected from the survey did not support the research hypotheses. The first hypothesis which stated that parenting styles will significantly influence self-esteem was not supported as the results were not in line with the research proposition. Hence, parenting styles did not significantly influence self-esteem of adolescents in public senior secondary schools in Abraka. However, that there was no significance between parenting styles and self-esteem, this does not suggest that certain parenting styles do not influence or build a child's self-esteem. Although there exists a mixed finding towards strong and weak directions, the current finding is not in agreement with the extant literature. Literature on the link between parenting styles and self-esteem of adolescents in secondary schools' population is in dearth. Parenting styles have strongly and weakly influenced self-esteem. For example, Lynn and Ting, (2019) who examined the influence of parenting style and self-esteem of adolescents on their groups from a school. Lynn and Ting, (2019) discovered that authoritative parenting style is the most dominant method used in modern family. Through this sort of parenting style, reasoning and communication between parents and children are

emphasized, and a balance between warmth and control are discovered. According to Lynn and Ting, (2019) majority of the respondents have mentioned a fair level of self-esteem, with only one student explains via permissive parenting style and the self-esteem is inferior compared to the others. Subsequently, the differences of parenting styles are influencing the students' self-esteem (Lynn & Ting, 2019). Hosogi et al., (2012) who showed that there was a correlation between certain parenting styles and higher or lower levels of global self-esteem in children. Similar research by Martínez and García (2007) found that children of indulgent parents had the highest levels of self-esteem while children of authoritarian parents had the lowest. Another study done later by Martínez and García (2008) found that adolescents with indulgent parents had equal or higher levels of self-esteem than adolescents with authoritative parents. Garcia and Gracia (2009) found that both the children of indulgent parenting style as well as the authoritative parenting styles had the highest levels of self-esteem. Antonopoulou et al., (2012) stated that the quality of supportiveness as perceived by the child predicted higher levels of implicit self-esteem in a study conducted. This means it is likely that children with neglecting parents would have lower levels of self-esteem. Furthermore, parents who were recognized as more nurturing (authoritative and permissive) had a positive effect on their children's self-esteem, while parents perceived to be overprotective (authoritarian) had a negative effect (Wagner et al., 2012). Additionally, emotional warmth (authoritative and permissive) has been positively correlated with higher levels of self-esteem, while negative loving, anger and rejecting

were negatively correlated (Erol & Orth, 2011). Okunlola et al., (2020) find out the prevalent style of parenting among the reviewed studies and establish the relationship between parenting styles and adolescents' self-esteem. According to Okunlola et al., (2020), authoritative parenting style was found to have had the greatest impact on adolescent self-esteem; it enhanced the highest self-esteem levels of adolescents above other parenting styles. Parents who are understanding and supportive tend to help their adolescents retain healthy self-esteem (Niaraki & Rahimi, 2013).

The second hypothesis which stated that parenting styles will significantly influence decision making style was not totally supported as the results were not in line with the proposed hypothesis. It was the neglectful parenting style that had a significance influence on decision making style of adolescents in public senior secondary schools in Abraka. This result is not in congruence with the extant literature that have investigated strong positive relationship between parenting styles and decision-making style of adolescents. Though, some proponents have supported that there is a link between parenting styles and decision-making style. Such as, Martensen and Gronholdt, (2008) who examined parents' perceptions of their children's participation (5-13 years) in the process of making family decisions when buying 14 different product categories. Martensen and Gronholdt, (2008) findings, indicated that parenting style impact children and have a strong influence on the family's decision-making process, especially for products that are relevant to them (such as cereals, juices, soft drinks, and cellphones). Simanjuntak and Rizkillah,

(2020) reported that parents have an essential role to improve the ability of children in decision-making and it important for parents begin to involve children in making decisions and build balanced family communication patterns with the children and parents' orientation. Altaf et al., (2020) examined the relationship of parenting styles with decision-making. However, the result in this study does not agree with Altaf et al., (2020) who showed that Decision making style is also significantly correlated with parenting styles. Parenting style is a significant contributing factor in the lives of adolescents having a substantial influence on their major life domains such as decision making (Rizvi & Najam 2015). Decision-making ability might be a vital part of transition during developmental phase of life. Prior research establishes that children's involvement in decisions (either deciding with parents or deciding on their own) increases over ages nine to 13 (Yee & Flanagan 1985), while decision autonomy (deciding without parental input) increases over ages 12 to 17 (Dornbusch, Carlsmith et al. 1985).

A possible reason that could have caused the observed difference in the study is the type of questions adopted to measure parenting styles, self-esteem and decision-making style. There is a possibility that common method bias impacted the questionnaire. This can be due to the sensitivity of the questions and the number of items on the questionnaire.

5.2 Conclusion

Parenting practices and adolescents' self-esteem and decision-making style have been analyzed. However, the results did not show strong positive relationships. Parents' authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful parenting styles all did not have a strong significance influence on how adolescents develop self-esteem and decision-making style. That is not to say, that effective parenting may not influence self-esteem and decision-making style of adolescents, especially in fostering good self-esteem and sound decision-making abilities. Based on the results of the study it is safe to state that:

1. Parenting styles do not significantly influence self-esteem of adolescents in public senior secondary schools in Abraka. This indicates that the nurture in which the parents give to their adolescent children does not determine the children's self-esteem.
2. Parenting styles do not significantly influence decision making style of adolescents in public senior secondary schools in Abraka. This indicates that parenting styles do not account for the adolescents' decision-making style. However, there was a significance correlation between neglectful parenting style and decision-making style. This suggests that adolescents experiencing neglectful parenting may be more likely to exhibit impaired decision-making skills.

5.3 Limitation and Suggestions for Further Studies

This study did not indicate significance influence of parenting styles on self-esteem and decision-making style of adolescents. Due to the fact that the results showed no strong

significance relationship between parenting styles, self-esteem and decision-making styles of adolescents. Though, only one dimension (neglectful) of parenting styles showed a significance relationship with decision making style. Nevertheless, some weaknesses linked to the methodology adopted in the study exist. First, the use of cross-sectional research design might hamper the ability to draw conclusion of cause-and-effect among the study variables. Second, the sample size might be small for the study, and the study only focused on just public senior secondary schools in Abraka, which might limit generalizability of research findings. Finally, all constructs were measured only by self-reported questionnaire (a subjective measure). As such, objective data was not collected. Further research is therefore needed to understand the mechanism of the relationships studied in this research. In further research the sample population should not be limited to just public schools. And further research should investigate the dimensions of decision-making styles into the work.

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